

GROQ-SEQ PLATFORM

Technical Bulletin for GROQ-seq TEV Protease Function Assay

A technical bulletin on the onboarding of a tobacco etch virus (TEV) protease assay to the GROQ-seq platform.

- Provides technical overview of the assay produced in our original TEV protease proposal¹
- Uses a gene circuit to tie TEV protease activity to bacterial cell growth
- Produces calibrated function measurements spanning an approximate 100-fold dynamic range.
- Measured over 18,000 TEV protease variants across 24 different experimental conditions

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Overview

The goal of this project was to develop a pooled assay for measuring tobacco etch virus (TEV) protease function using the Growth-Based Quantitative Sequencing (GROQ-seq) platform². Previous work on engineering proteases has demonstrated the ability to evolve proteases with altered specificity relevant to hepatitis C³, botulinum neurotoxin⁴, and systemic challenges such as pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-2⁵. To our knowledge, no comprehensive deep mutational scanning (DMS) study across the entire TEV protease protein has been reported in the over three decades since its identification, leaving key aspects of its sequence–function landscape unexplored. Understanding the full mutational landscape of TEV protease can enable new insights and pathways for engineering the activity and specificity of future protease variants.

The assay described in this technical bulletin works by linking TEV protease function to cellular fitness. This is achieved using a plasmid where the TEV protease’s substrate is implemented as the linker of a split dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) protein. DHFR expression confers resistance to trimethoprim (TMP); therefore, changes in TEV protease function, impacting the cleavage of the split-DHFR system, translates into modulation of TMP resistance. Changes in TMP resistance are then measured as differences in cellular growth (fitness) across four timepoints. Variants are uniquely barcoded, enabling pooled sequencing-based measurement of relative fitness. Importantly, a barcoded ladder of calibration variants is included in every pool, ensuring reproducibility across experimental batches.

The pilot dataset generated by the GROQ-seq TEV protease assay can be accessed at data.alignbio.org. The pilot dataset generated quantitative TEV protease function data for two libraries: a site-saturation variant library (SSVL) and an error-prone PCR (epPCR) library (see the Dataset Description section for additional details). The long-term objective of generating these datasets is to enable the development of predictive models that can infer the effects of mutations on TEV protease function directly from protein sequence.

The assay described in this technical report currently supports TEV protease variants, but it can be readily expanded to systematically explore additional proteases, substrates, and assay conditions. The ability to explore the mutational landscape of both protease and substrate sequences within a single-plasmid system presents a unique opportunity to generate large-scale protein–protein interaction datasets. This assay could be extended to measure interactions across a wide range of proteases and substrates, including structural homologs of TEV protease as well as non-canonical substrate sequences. In future work, kinetic functional measurements of the calibration variants can also be determined, allowing relative fitness measurements to be converted into quantitative functional values.

Assay Details

Assay Characteristics

- This assay can produce calibrated function measurements across a 100-fold dynamic range⁶.
- To assess biological reproducibility, two barcode measurements of the same amino acid variant were randomly sampled. Measurements were highly consistent, with strong correlations (Spearman $\rho = 0.895$) and low error was observed (RMSE = 0.148)⁶.
- To assess protocol reproducibility, the GROQ-seq assay was repeated on two separate days using the TEV SSVL library. Measurements were highly consistent across runs with strong correlations (Spearman $\rho = 0.950$) and low error (RMSE = 0.106)⁶.

Figure 4. Range of measured TEV protease function from the dataset presented in this report. Protease expression is derived from Van induction to drive transcription. $\log(\text{DHFR})$ represents the final quantity of intact DHFR. Low DHFR and High DHFR conditions were induced by 10 μM and 25 μM Sal.

Protocols

Prior to integration into the GROQ-seq, barcode-variant associations are established for each plasmid in the TEV protease variant library using long-read nanopore sequencing. Variant libraries are then introduced into the GROQ-seq TEV protease experimental pipeline (Fig. 1), which consists of three main phases*:

1. TEV Protease Pooled Growth-Based Assay
2. DNA Extraction⁷
3. BarSeq Preparation and Pooling

**For an in-depth description of each phase, including protocols, required reagents, consumables, and hardware, see the respective files in the Supplemental Materials for reference.*

After these three phases are complete, the pooled samples are sent for Illumina sequencing, and resulting sequencing reads are analyzed using our computational pipeline. To access the complete computational pipeline for analyzing these experiments go to:

<https://github.com/Align-to-Innovate/groqseq-pipeline>.

Figure 1: A high-level overview of the GROQ-seq experimental pipeline.

Measurement Strain

The host strain is Marionette-Clo (sAJM.1504)⁸, which is an *E. coli* DH10B-derived strain with the 12 optimized biosensors of the Marionette system integrated in the genome. This host strain was chosen for the TEV protease GROQ-seq assay due to its relatively high transformation efficiency and integration of the Marionette cluster, which allows orthogonal and tunable induction of the TEV variant library and substrate via ligand induction for multi-parametric biophysical measurements. Marionette-Clo (sAJM.1504) may be accessed from AddGene (Watertown, Massachusetts).

Circuit Design

The GROQ-seq TEV protease assay employs a gene circuit connecting TEV protease function to growth using an antibiotic resistance gene as a selection marker (Fig. 2). In the TEV protease plasmid circuit, each variant is expressed from a uniquely barcoded plasmid with an N-terminal maltose-binding protein (MBP) tag. On the same plasmid, a split-DHFR is expressed whereby the TEV substrate links two units of DHFR (DHFR1,2 - TEV substrate - DHFR3). Therefore, if the TEV substrate within the DHFR is successfully cleaved by the TEV protease variant expressed, DHFR is destroyed, increasing the sensitivity to TMP. In this system, TEV protease and DHFR expression are independently inducible, enabling multi-parameter biophysical measurements by titrating the concentrations of both the enzyme and its substrate. The GenBank file for the base library plasmid of TEV protease can be found in the Supplemental Materials.

The circuit is implemented with the vanillic acid (Van) and salicylic acid (Sal) inducible promoters from the *E. coli* Marionette system⁸. These promoters were selected for their low basal transcriptional activity, high dynamic range, and orthogonal ligand responses to minimize cassette crosstalk. In this circuit, TEV expression is under control of the Van inducible promoter and the split-DHFR expression is under control of the Sal inducible promoter.

Figure 2: The GROQ-seq TEV protease assay's plasmid diagram. Illustrating the barcode region, expression cassette, selection cassette, and backbone.

Expression Cassette

The expression cassette contains an operon which enables inducible expression of the TEV protease gene. In our system, the sequence used as the wild type (WT) background for library construction includes the S219V substitution, a stabilizing mutation that confers resistance to autoproteolysis. The N-terminal MBP fusion solubilizes the TEV variant for stable expression in *E. coli*. TEV expression is regulated by the P_{VanCC} promoter, which is repressed by the high-functioning VanR^{AM} regulator and is induced by Van, enabling up to a 1100-fold dynamic range in transcriptional output⁸. VanR^{AM} is resistant to Sal, the ligand used to induce expression in our selection cassette. The initial transcribed region contains a self-cleaving ribozyme to normalize the 5' mRNA transcript end. During circuit tuning, an 8.5k bicistronic design (BCD) element was found to confer a wide dynamic range and high resolution function measurements across the 25 calibration variants.

Selection Cassette

The selection cassette contains an operon which enables inducible expression of a split DHFR adjoined by a linker containing the TEV protease substrate. Expression of the split DHFR system is regulated by the P_{SalTTC} promoter, which is regulated by the high-functioning NahR^{AM} repressor to enable induction by Sal for up to a 760-fold dynamic range of transcriptional output⁸. NahR^{AM} is resistant to Van induction, the ligand used to induce expression in our expression cassette. Like the expression cassette, the 5' mRNA transcript end is normalized by a self-cleaving ribozyme, and a 8.5k BCD element yielded high resolution measurements between the calibration variants.

Barcode Region

This plasmid utilizes a dual barcode system to create a vast diversity of barcodes, enabling each protein variant to be uniquely identified, often with multiple barcodes per variant. The system consists of two barcode halves separated by a homology region, where each of the barcode halves takes the form NNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNNWSNNN. For additional information about the barcoding strategy please refer to the GROQ-seq Platform Proposal (section 4.2.1: Barcode Region)².

Backbone

The backbone used for variant libraries in this work is pTwist Kan Medium Copy from Twist Biosciences (South San Francisco, CA). This backbone contains a p15A origin of replication and a kanamycin resistance marker.

Plasmids

Base Library Plasmids

The GenBank file for the TEV Protease base library plasmid (Table 1) is included in the Supplemental Materials. This uses what was defined as the wild-type (WT) variant of TEV Protease. This plasmid includes annotations for circuit components as well as the parts used in Golden Gate cloning.

Calibration and Normalization Plasmids

Both calibration and normalization variant controls were used in this assay (Table 1), and their GenBank files can be found in the Supplemental Materials. These control variants will enable the conversion of sequencing-based fitness into quantitative functional values (for more details see the GROQ-seq platform proposal², section 8: Data Analysis and Machine Learning Evaluation).

Two well-characterized normalization variants, previously developed for the GROQ-seq Transcription Factor (TF) Assay, were used alongside an additional mDHFR variant to function as ‘always-high’ variants. The similarity of assay conditions between the TF and TEV protease GROQ-seq assays enabled calibration variants not requiring inducers or ligands to be shared between these assays.

Table 1: GROQ-seq TEV Protease assay plasmids

Name	Variant Description
pTEV-WT_BasePlasmid	TEV Protease Base Library Plasmid
pRamR-norm-02	Normalization Variant
pLacI-norm-02	Normalization Variant
pNorm-mDFHR-03	Normalization Variant
pDRAC1-TEV29	Calibration Variant 1
pDRAC3-TEV29	Calibration Variant 2
pDRAC5-TEV7	Calibration Variant 3
pDRAC7-TEV7	Calibration Variant 4
pDRAC9-TEV11	Calibration Variant 5
pDRAC11-TEV11	Calibration Variant 6
pDRAC13-TEV15	Calibration Variant 7

Table 1 Continued: GROQ-seq TEV Protease assay plasmids

pDRAC15-TEV15	Calibration Variant 8
pDRAC17-TEV17	Calibration Variant 9
pDRAC18-TEV18	Calibration Variant 10
pDRAC19-TEV19	Calibration Variant 11
pDRAC20-TEV20	Calibration Variant 12
pDRAC21-TEV21	Calibration Variant 13
pDRAC22-TEV22	Calibration Variant 14
pDRAC23-TEV23	Calibration Variant 15
pDRAC24-TEV24	Calibration Variant 16
pDRAC25-TEV25	Calibration Variant 17
pDRAC26-TEV26	Calibration Variant 18
pDRAC27-TEV29	Calibration Variant 19
pDRAC28-TEV29	Calibration Variant 20
pDRAC29-TEV29	Calibration Variant 21
pDRAC30-TEV29	Calibration Variant 22
pDRAC31-TEV7	Calibration Variant 23
pDRAC32-TEV11	Calibration Variant 24
pDRAC33-TEV15	Calibration Variant 25

Experimental Design

Selection Marker

This assay is challenged by trimethoprim (TMP) at the following concentrations:

- 0 µg/mL
- 3 µg/mL

Inducers

The circuit is implemented with the vanillic acid (Van) and salicylic acid (Sal) inducible promoters from the E. coli Marionette system. Van induces TEV expression and Sal induces DHFR expression. They were used at the following concentrations:

- Sal was used to induce DHFR expression at:
 - 0 $\mu\text{mol/L}$
 - 10 $\mu\text{mol/L}$
 - 25 $\mu\text{mol/L}$
- Van was used to induce TEV expression for both:
 - A 6-fold dilution series ($\mu\text{mol/L}$): 200, 33, 5.5, and 0
 - A 2-fold dilution series ($\mu\text{mol/L}$): 200, 100, 50, 25, 12, 6.3, 3.1, 1.6, 0.8, and 0

Plate map

To systematically characterize TEV protease activity across a range of expression and selection regimes, we evaluated the TEV protease libraries under multiple experimental conditions. The libraries were evaluated across 24 conditions, each performed with four replicates on the same plate. Each condition varied along three parameters: TMP concentration, TEV protease expression level (Van concentration), and DHFR expression level (Sal concentration). The platemap resulting from testing all antibiotic and inducer conditions can be seen below.

Figure 3: The GROQ-seq TEV protease assay plate map.

Dataset Description

The initial dataset collected by GROQ-seq TEV protease assay is publicly accessible through our data portal (data.alignbio.org), enabling direct access, reuse, and integration with other protein function datasets. This dataset was collected at the Living Measurements Systems Foundry (LMSF) at the National Institute of Standards and Technology.

Variant Library Overview & Synthesis

This data release includes data for two different types of libraries:

- Site-Saturation Variant Library (SSVL): a library consisting of variants with all possible single-amino-acid substitutions. The SSVL library was purchased from Twist Bioscience (South San Francisco, California). The quality control report for the SSVL library can be found in the Supplemental Materials.
 - Some positions were missing from the gene library synthesis used for the SSVL libraries. Those missing positions are G36 and N52.
 - Overall, this dataset covers 92% of the possible single amino acid substitutions, insertions, and deletions.
- Error-prone PCR (epPCR): a library generated using epPCR amplification of the TEV protease coding sequence, with a mean non-synonymous mutation coding sequence of 5 mutations per variant in the epPCR library. The epPCR library was purchased from GenScript USA Inc. (Piscataway, NJ).

Cloning & Transformation

Protein variant libraries and random barcodes were cloned into the GROQ-seq TEV protease backbone plasmid using a 5-part Golden Gate assembly. This process was performed by Clutch Biotechnologies (Burlingame, California). The parts designed for Golden Gate assembly can be found as annotations in the TEV protease base plasmid with the category labeled 'Clutch' (attached in Supplemental Materials).

All libraries were first cloned in NEB® 10-beta Competent *E. coli* (c3019-DHI0B) from New England Biolabs (Ipswich, MA) before being run through the GROQ-seq platform.

Barcode Mapping

In order to map variant sequences to their unique barcodes, long-read sequencing was performed on all variant libraries. Long-read sequencing was performed by Plasmidsaurus (South San Francisco, CA).

Sequencing

For all samples coming out of the GROQ-seq TEV protease assay, enrichment of each variant was determined by sequencing the number of barcodes present via short-read sequencing. Samples were sent to Novogene (Sacramento, CA) for barcode sequencing. All samples were sequenced with a 25B-read flow cell.

Data Analysis

To access the complete computational pipeline used to analyze these experiments go to: <https://github.com/Align-to-Innovate/groqseq-pipeline>. For additional specific information about data analysis and cleaning, please refer to the README attached as a supplemental download at <https://data.alignbio.org/>.

Barcode Quality Sieve

Table 2. Barcode quality sieve – TEV protease libraries (TEV-EP and TEV-SSVL)

Sequential quality filters applied independently to the TEV-EP and TEV-SSVL libraries. Percentage retained is cumulative relative to each library's initial barcode count.

Filter		TEV-EP			TEV-SSVL		
Step	Description	Remaining	Removed	% Retained	Remaining	Removed	% Retained
Start	Initial barcode dataset All barcodes from Bartender clustering assigned to TEV protease libraries.	24,336	—	100.0%	46,920	—	100.0%
1	High-confidence protein sequence required Each barcode must have a reliable consensus coding sequence from Nanopore long reads: ≥60% of reads must agree on one sequence, or the multi-sequence alignment quality must be ≥30 at every base. Frame-shifted sequences are excluded.	18,269	6,067	75.1%	45,447	1,473	96.9%
2	Bayesian fitness passed convergence check The Bayesian fitness model fit must pass the R-hat convergence diagnostic, indicating the posterior is well-sampled.	18,260	9	75.0%	45,443	4	96.9%
3	Plasmid length matches expected size Modal Nanopore read length must fall within bounds expected for an intact 5,751 bp plasmid. Barcodes with reads that are too long are presumed to carry backbone insertions; those with reads that are too short are presumed to carry deletions. The lower bound relaxes at low read depth where length estimates are less reliable (see note a).	12,785	5,475	52.5%	34,702	10,741	74.0%

Filter		TEV-EP			TEV-SSVL		
Step	Description	Remaining	Removed	% Retained	Remaining	Removed	% Retained
4	All backbone elements present For barcodes with sufficient Nanopore reads, every backbone element must be covered by the expected number of reads, 0.6 times the total number of Nanopore reads for the barcode, with a relaxed threshold at lower read count to allow for Poisson sampling errors (kanamycin resistance cassette, origin of replication, MBP-TEV fusion and its regulatory sequences, DHFR-substrate and its regulatory region, linker-substrate sequence; see note b).	12,784	1	52.5%	34,702	0	74.0%
5	Zero-antibiotic fitness within expected range Barcodes with implausible fitness values under zero-trimethoprim conditions are removed. Thresholds are derived from the distribution of wild-type barcodes under the same conditions (see note c).	10,056	2,728	41.3%	29,901	4,801	63.7%
6	Backbone element sequences are correct When critical backbone elements are sequenced with high confidence, they must exactly match the expected reference sequence (DHFR-substrate and its regulatory region, the regulatory region for MBP-TEV, origin of replication). Barcodes where a checked element is present but sequenced at low confidence are retained (see note d).	9,750	306	40.1%	29,320	581	62.5%
Final	Clean dataset	9,750	14,586	40.1%	29,320	17,600	62.5%

Overall retention (steps 1–6): TEV-EP: 9,750 / 24,336 barcodes retained (40.1%) TEV-SSVL: 29,320 / 46,920 barcodes retained (62.5%)

Filter definitions for barcode quality sieve

- (a)** Plasmid length. The upper bound is 1.03 times the expected plasmid size (5,751 bp), giving a threshold of 5,923 bp. The lower bound is read-depth dependent: a barcode is retained if the modal Nanopore read length divided by the expected plasmid length exceeds 0.98 minus 0.6 divided by the number of long reads. This threshold becomes less stringent at low read depth, where length estimates are less reliable, and approaches 98% of the expected length asymptotically at high read depth.
- (b)** Backbone elements. The 13 elements checked are: kanamycin resistance cassette (two regions), p15a origin of replication (two regions), MBP-TEV linker sequence, MBP regulatory sequence, TEV protease regulatory sequence, DHFR selection marker (two regions), DHFR regulatory sequence, and linker-substrate sequence. Each backbone element must be covered by the expected number of reads, 0.6 times the total number of Nanopore reads for the barcode, with a relaxed threshold at lower read count to allow for Poisson sampling errors.
- (c)** Zero-antibiotic fitness filter. Under zero-trimethoprim conditions, all functional variants are expected to grow at a rate consistent with the wild type. The fitness distribution of wild-type barcodes under zero trimethoprim is used to define acceptable upper and lower bounds; barcodes falling outside those bounds are removed. This excludes variants with aberrant growth that is independent of TEV protease activity.
- (d)** Backbone sequence correctness. The six elements checked are: DHFR selection marker (two regions), linker-substrate sequence, DHFR regulatory region, MBP-TEV regulatory region, and the p15a origin of replication. Sequence checking is applied only when the element is covered at high confidence ($\geq 60\%$ of reads must agree on one sequence, or the multi-sequence alignment quality must be ≥ 30 at every base); barcodes where an element is present but covered at low confidence are retained rather than excluded. Barcodes where a checked element does not match the reference are presumed to carry a backbone mutation that could affect plasmid function independently of the gene of interest.

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